

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

EFFECT OF A MIXTURE OF SWEET CLOVER, ST. JOHN'S WORT AND PURSLANE EXTRACTS ON THE ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF YOGURT

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Abstract

The use of plant extracts in the production of functional dairy products is one of the relevant directions in modern food technology. Plant extracts can increase the nutritional and biological value of yogurt and improve its antioxidant properties. This study investigated the effect of a mixture of sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts on the antioxidant activity of yogurt. The extract mixture was added to yogurt in an amount of 1 ml. The ratio of plant components in the mixture was 35:35:30, 35:30:35 and 40:25:35. Yogurt without added extracts was used as a control sample. The results showed that the addition of plant extract mixtures increased the antioxidant activity of yogurt. The TEAC value of the control yogurt was 50.80 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$, while the fortified yogurt samples showed values ranging from 63.00 to 74.03 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$. The highest antioxidant activity was observed in yogurt enriched with the mixture of sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts at a ratio of 35:30:35. In this sample, the TEAC value reached 74.03 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$, which was approximately 45.7% higher than that of the control sample. The obtained results indicate the prospects of using a mixture of sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts as a natural functional additive in yogurt production. This mixture can increase the antioxidant potential of yogurt and contribute to expanding the range of functional dairy products.

Keywords: yogurt, sweet clover, St. John's wort, purslane, plant extracts, antioxidant activity, TEAC, functional dairy products.

Introduction

Currently, the development of functional food products is one of the important areas of the food industry. Consumer demand for products enriched with natural components and biologically active substances is increasing. In this regard, the enrichment of dairy products, including yogurt, with plant extracts is considered a relevant technological approach [1].

Yogurt is a fermented dairy product with high nutritional value, good digestibility and a beneficial effect on the intestinal microflora. It contains proteins, fats, vitamins, minerals and lactic acid microorganisms. However, in modern functional food technology, special attention is paid not only to the nutritional value of yogurt, but also to improving its antioxidant and biologically active properties [2, 3].

Plant extracts contain phenolic compounds, flavonoids, organic acids, vitamins and other biologically active substances. These components can increase the antioxidant activity of the product and enhance its functional significance [4, 5]. The use of medicinal plant extracts in yogurt production is an effective way to introduce natural functional additives into dairy products [6].

Sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane are plants rich in biologically active compounds. Sweet clover contains coumarins and phenolic compounds; St. John's wort is rich in flavonoids and substances with

antioxidant activity; purslane is known as a source of vitamins, organic acids and natural antioxidants [7, 8]. The use of these plant extracts in the form of a mixture can improve the functional properties of yogurt.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of a mixture of sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts on the antioxidant activity of yogurt and to determine the most effective ratio of plant components.

Materials and methods

Yogurt samples enriched with a mixture of plant extracts were used as the object of the study. Yogurt without added extracts was used as the control sample. Experimental samples were prepared by adding a mixture of sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts.

The extract mixture was added to yogurt in an amount of 1 ml. The ratio of plant components in the mixture was 35:35:30, 35:30:35 and 40:25:35. These ratios characterize the percentage share of sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts in the mixture.

The antioxidant activity of yogurt samples was determined using the ABTS method [9]. The results were calculated as Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC) and expressed as $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$. The obtained values were compared with the control sample in order to evaluate the effect of the plant extract mixture on the antioxidant activity of yogurt.

Results and discussion

The results of evaluating the effect of mixtures of sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts on

the antioxidant activity of yogurt are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Antioxidant activity of yogurt samples enriched with mixtures of plant extracts

Sample name	Extract ratio	TEAC, $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$
Control yogurt	No extract added	50.80
Yogurt + extract mixture	35:35:30	63.00
Yogurt + extract mixture	35:30:35	74.03
Yogurt + extract mixture	40:25:35	71.71

The results showed that the addition of plant extract mixtures increased the antioxidant activity of yogurt. The TEAC value of the control sample was 50.80 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$. In the experimental samples containing sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts, this indicator ranged from 63.00 to 74.03 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$.

The yogurt sample containing the extract mixture at a ratio of 35:35:30 had a TEAC value of 63.00 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$, which was higher than that of the control sample. In the sample with the 40:25:35 ratio, antioxidant activity reached 71.71 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$.

The highest result was observed in yogurt enriched with the mixture of sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts at a ratio of 35:30:35. In this sample, the TEAC value was 74.03 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$. Compared with the control sample, antioxidant activity increased by approximately 45.7%. This result indicates that the studied plant extract mixture can improve the functional properties of yogurt.

The increase in antioxidant activity may be associated with the presence of phenolic compounds, flavonoids and other biologically active substances in the plant extracts. Therefore, the use of a mixture of sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts in yogurt production can be considered a promising direction for the development of functional dairy products [10].

Conclusion

The results of the study showed that the use of a mixture of sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts in yogurt production increases the antioxidant activity of the product. Compared with the control sample without extracts, all experimental samples had higher TEAC values.

The highest antioxidant activity was determined in yogurt enriched with the extract mixture at a ratio of 35:30:35. In this sample, the TEAC value was 74.03 $\mu\text{mol TE/g}$, which was approximately 45.7% higher than that of the control sample.

The obtained results confirm the possibility of using plant extract mixtures as effective natural functional additives for yogurt enrichment. The mixture based on sweet clover, St. John's wort and purslane extracts can improve the functional properties of yogurt and contribute to the development of new dairy products with high antioxidant potential.

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References

1. Nistor O.V., Andronoiu D.G., Botez E., et al. Assessment of the antioxidant activity and quality attributes of yogurt enhanced with wild herbs extracts // *Journal of Food Quality*. 2018. Vol. 2018. Article ID 5329386.
2. Joung J.Y., Lee J.Y., Ha Y.S., Shin Y.K., Kim Y., Kim S.H., Oh N.S. Enhanced microbial, functional and sensory properties of herbal yogurt fermented with Korean traditional plant extracts // *Korean Journal for Food Science of Animal Resources*. 2016. Vol. 36, No. 1. P. 65–72.
3. Kesenkas H., Dertli E., Kınık Ö., Öztürk H.I., Akgül E. The effect of plant extracts on antioxidant potential, microbial and sensory attributes of stirred yoghurt // *Mljekarstvo*. 2020. Vol. 70, No. 4. P. 272–283.
4. Shori A.B. Storage quality and antioxidant properties of yogurt fortified with polyphenol extract from nutmeg, black pepper, and white pepper // *Electronic Journal of Biotechnology*. 2022. Vol. 57. P. 24–30.
5. Liu Y.T., Gong Y., Xie Y., et al. Chemical constituents and antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-tumor activities of *Melilotus officinalis* (L.) Pall. // *Molecules*. 2018. Vol. 23, No. 2. Article 271.
6. Assessment report on *Melilotus officinalis* (L.) Lam., herba // *European Medicines Agency. Committee on Herbal Medicinal Products*. London, 2016. 42 p.
7. Ivanova I., Denev P., Todorova M., et al. Development of dairy products fortified with plant extracts // *Functional Foods in Health and Disease*. 2023. Vol. 13, No. 2. P. 65–85.
8. Siddiqui N., Rauf A., Latif A., Mahmood Z. Spectrophotometric determination of the total phenolic content, spectral and fluorescence study of the herbal Unani drug Gul-e-Zoofa // *Journal of Taibah University Medical Sciences*. 2017. Vol. 12, No. 4. P. 360–363.
9. Ramos R.T.M., Bezerra I.C.F., Ferreira M.R.A., Soares L.A.L. Spectrophotometric quantification of flavonoids in herbal material, crude extract, and fractions from leaves of *Eugenia uniflora* Linn. // *Pharmacognosy Research*. 2017. Vol. 9, No. 3. P. 253–260.
10. Alamoudi S.A., Saad A.M., Alsubhi N.H., et al. Upgrading the physicochemical and sensory quality of yogurt by incorporating polyphenol-enriched citrus pomaces with antioxidant, antimicrobial, and antitumor activities // *Frontiers in Nutrition*. 2022. Vol. 9. Article 999581.